

Configurational Analyses of post-disaster scenarios for the Porto Alegre Metropolitan Area Floodings (May 2024)

(V1.0)

Welsh School of Architecture
Ysgol Pensaerïaeth Cymru

INSTITUTO
NACIONAL DE PESQUISAS
HIDRÁULICAS

GESPLA
Gabinete de Estudos e
Planejamento Urbano
e Territorial

Cardiff, 13th November 2024

Context & Methodology

The document **Configurational Analyses of post-disaster scenarios for the Porto Alegre Metropolitan Area Floodings** is a technical-cartographical effort originally prepared in an emergency-response context, to showcase and evaluate the main disruption points and vulnerabilities in terms of accessibility, redundancy and movement patterns within the road-circulation networks of Porto Alegre's, Grande Porto Alegre's, and Vale dos Sinos regions, affected by severe floodings from May 2nd, 2024.

This evaluation is made through simulations that consider four scenarios:

- **Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0):** Pre-disaster road-network, without flooding and under normal conditions.
- **Scenario 1:** Scenario post-disaster, considering the road interruptions upon intersection with the verified flooded area on 6th-8th May 2024.
- **Scenario 2:** Hypothetical scenario post-disaster, considering the verified flooded area on 6th-8th May 2024, plus an interruption of the RS-118 state highway. This road-element was the single remaining point of connection of Porto Alegre's greater metropolitan area in Scenario 1, and at risk after 6th May 2024.
- **Scenario 3:** Scenario post-disaster 1, considering the addition of the emergency humanitarian corridor opened on 10th May 2024. It reconnected Porto Alegre's city centre flooded access to the elevated highway network, providing another redundancy to the RS-118.

Graphs were open-sourced from the OpenStreetMap (OSM – Planet OSM, 2024) database and modelled in DepthMapX 0.8, using Space Syntax Normalised Angular Segment Analysis (ASA) and in MATLAB, for the Normalised Kemeny-based Centrality, ASA is a network-based model that highlights both patterns of *relative accessibility* (NAIN) – estimating movement potentials – and *preferential route choice* (NACH) – estimating flow probabilities – in a system. Both models can be constructed in radius n (system) and in several metric radii associated to different types of mobility, described as following (Hillier & Hanson, 1984; Turner, 2001; Hillier, Yang, Turner, 2012; Van Nes, Yamu, 2021). The Normalised Kemeny-Based Centrality (NKBC) is a network measure that estimates the degree of redundancy of an element within the system, or how important it is in terms of overall connectivity. A high NKBC means a low redundancy, thus higher risk.

Space Syntax Formula	Concept Explanation
$AIn = 1/2((1/k-1)\sum d_{Ck}) / k-2) / D_k$	Measures farness between network elements, considering their count (k) and the system angular total depth sum ($\sum d_{Ck}$); or topological distance between network elements. Denotes a road-element relative accessibility or movement potential (to-movement), informing how reachable, in comparison to all others in the system, it is thus its closeness centrality. The normalized formula relativizes angular total depth and allows comparisons between different systems [17,27].
$NAIN_{Rn} = k^{-2} / \sum d_{Ck}$	At metric radiuses, NAIN indicates the spatial hierarchies and distribution of local sub-centres of relative accessibility, as well as their density [17,28].
$NAIN_{Rmetric} = \log(AIn) + 2$	
$ACH = \sum \sum_{i \neq j} g^{(i \rightarrow j \rightarrow k)}$	Sums the number of times a road-element is traversed, through the shortest paths route, considering all origin-destination pairs. Denotes the hierarchies of preferential routes choice (flow probabilities, through-movement), thus its betweenness centrality. The normalized formula relativizes angular total depth and allows comparisons between different systems [17,27].
$NACH_{Rn} = \log(ACH+1) / \log(\sum d_{Ck}) + 3$	At metric radiuses, NACH indicates the spatial hierarchies of the local sub-centres, informing their weight for the intermediate preferential routes structure [17,28].
$NACH_{Rmetric} = \log(ACH) + 2$	
$K(P) = \sum 1/(r + \lambda)$ $NKBC = K(\hat{P}) - K(P)$	The Normalised Kemeny-based centrality is based on a Page Rank Markov Process which uses the graph's Kemeny constant $K(P)$ to calculate an edge centrality measure. This centrality can be interpreted as the "weak-ties", describing also the degree of redundancy for each element in the system. Each Markov iteration results in a different $K(P)$ that are ranked in the final measure

Distance	Measure	Type	Significance
400m	R400	Metric	Local (Pedestrian)
800m	R800	Metric	Local (Pedestrian)
1200m	R1200	Metric	Local (Pedestrian, 15 Minute City, X Minute City)
2000m	R2000	Metric	Semi-Local (Pedestrian); Local (Vehicular-Motorised)
5000m	R5000	Metric	Local (Vehicular-Motorised)
n (system)	Rn	Topological	Global (Vehicular-Motorised)

The network models are presented within a GIS-based environment (QGIS, 2024), spatialized and statistically distributed using an equal count (quartile) range. Maximum and minimum values are associated to each individual system showcasing its internal patterns of relative accessibility or preferential routes in visualisation. Scenarios that have more than one system are numerically aggregated for attaining their overall element count, average and maximum values for each configurational measure, providing means of comparison with the stable road-network.

This analysis aims to provide actionable information for stakeholders and to raise awareness about the potential socio-spatial impacts of their decisions.

Diego Altafini

Decoding Cities for Informed Decision Making - DECIDE
UKRI/Marie Curie Post-Graduate Fellow
Welsh School of Architecture
Cardiff University

This work was made possible by a collaboration between the Cardiff University/Prifysgol Caerdydd - Welsh School of Architecture (WSA) - UK and the Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS) - Instituto de Pesquisas Hidráulicas (IPH)/GESPLA - Grupo de pesquisa em Planejamento e Gestão de Recursos Hídricos - Brazil. Involved researchers:

Diego Altafini (WSA), Camilla Pezziça (WSA), Clarice Bteil de Souza (WSA), Ana Paula Dalcin (UFRGS/IPH), Guilherme Marques (UFRGS/IPH).

This research has received funding from the **United Kingdom Research and Innovation Post Doctoral Fellowship Guarantee Scheme, set over the European Union's Horizon Europe – Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions Post Doctoral Fellowships**. UKRI Grant no. 101107846-DECIDE/EP/Y028716/1. Views and opinions expressed are those of the authors only, and do not necessarily reflect those of the United Kingdom or European Union. Neither the United Kingdom or European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Porto Alegre's Metropolitan Area Road-Circulation Network - Overview of the flood affected area.

- Highways (OSM)
- Primary Roads (OSM)
- Secondary Roads (OSM)
- Local Road Circulation Network

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

• Normalised Kemeny-based Centrality

The pre-disaster scenario demonstrates Porto Alegre's Metropolitan area system-wide *Normalised Kemeny-based Centrality*. It indicates the roads that have a lower degree of redundancy on the system. The highway connections are points of fragility within the system, as they demonstrate high NKBC values, thus a low overall redundancy. Those are more important to the system cohesion.

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NAIN (Rn)

The pre-disaster scenario demonstrates Porto Alegre's Metropolitan area system-wide *relative accessibility* patterns under normal conditions. Areas with a high *accessibility* comprise the *centrality core* that structures movement potentials across the system. Areas with low accessibility tend to be segregated from the network standpoint, thus, harder to reach.

Patos' Lagoon

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NAIN (R400)

Metric-based pre-disaster scenarios demonstrate Porto Alegre's Metropolitan area *relative accessibility* patterns under normal conditions at local scales. Areas with a high accessibility comprise the *centrality cores* that structure movement potentials locally. Different radii give an overview about different modes of transport (small radii = pedestrian; large radii (vehicular-motorised).

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NAIN (R800)

High

Low

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NAIN (R1200)

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NAIN (R2000)

High

Low

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NAIN (R5000)

High

Low

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NACH (Rn)

This pre-disaster scenario demonstrates Porto Alegre's Metropolitan area system-wide *preferential route choice* patterns under normal conditions. Areas with a high value comprise the structures of flow and connection, most traversed across the system.

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NACH (R400)

This pre-disaster scenario demonstrates Porto Alegre's Metropolitan area system-wide *preferential route choice* patterns under normal conditions. Areas with a high value comprise local sub-centres, that connect the main *preferential routes'* structure for different transport modes

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NACH (R800)

High

Low

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NACH (R1200)

High

Low

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NACH (R2000)

High

Low

1:500,000

Stable Road Network - (Scenario 0)

- NACH (R5000)

High

Low

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NAIN (Rn)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the flooding impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. The highway interruption created three "isolated systems" of relative accessibility and affected the main centrality core structure at several points, segregating the northern urban areas. Movement is concentrated on the only preserved access at RS-118

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NAIN (R400)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the flooding impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. Local systems tend to maintain their cohesion at smaller scales, thus pedestrian movement potentials tend to be preserved. The system cohesiveness tend to worsen in larger scales, where impacts of the flooding event can be seen in the *relative accessibility* to vehicular-motorised traffic.

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NAIN (R800)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NAIN (R1200)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NAIN (R2000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NAIN (R5000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NACH (Rn)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the flooding impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. Important connections were made inaccessible after the flooding, which led to the complete collapse of the main axes of flow within the metropolitan area. The RS-118 structured all the flows between Porto Alegre and the areas on the north, constituting an extremely fragile system.

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NACH (R400)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NACH (R800)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NACH (R1200)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NACH (R2000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network on 6th May 2024 - (Scenario 1)

• NACH (R5000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NAIN (Rn)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the hypothetical interruption of the RS-118 upon the flooding and the overall impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. A total collapse of the connections between north and south would cause the creation of four "isolated systems", each with a distinctive centrality core. This would limit the accessibility towards the logistical hubs located in the municipality of Canoas, affecting early-disaster relief actions.

Flooded Area

Patos' Lagoon

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NAIN (R400)

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NAIN (R800)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NAIN (R1200)

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NAIN (R2000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NAIN (R5000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NACH (Rn)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the hypothetical interruption of the RS-118 upon the flooding and the overall impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. The loss of the RS-118 would split the metropolitan system, as this was the only local connection standing after the flood. It had to be preserved at all costs, at the risk of a total system collapse.

Patos' Lagoon

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NACH (R400)

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NACH (R800)

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NACH (R1200)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NACH (R2000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, simulating RS-118 interruption - (Scenario 2)

• NACH (R5000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NAIN (Rn)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the emergency corridor overall impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. Re-establishing the connection between Porto Alegre and Canoas through the BR-290 highway improves the overall relative accessibility, while also providing a redundancy to the at-risk RS-118. It brings the system closer to the pre-disaster spatial-configuration.

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NAIN (R400)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NAIN (R800)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NAIN (R1200)

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NAIN (R2000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NAIN (R5000)

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

- NACH (Rn)

This post-disaster scenario portrays the emergency corridor overall impact on Porto Alegre's metropolitan area system. Re-establishing the connection between Porto Alegre and Canoas through the BR-290 highway creates an alternative *preferential route choice*, thus improving the flows across the system. It was a crucial action that helped the relief efforts, shortening the distances between Porto Alegre and the Logistical Hub at the Municipality of Canoas.

Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NACH (R400)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NACH (R800)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NACH (R1200)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NACH (R2000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

Flooded Road Network, active Emergency Corridor - (Scenario 3)

• NACH (R5000)

 Flooded Area

1:500,000

References

Altafani, D., Bleil de Souza, C., Pezzica, C., Marques, G., Dalcin, A. (2024) Porto Alegre's Metropolitan Region Road Circulation Network Vulnerability Analysis - Floods of 2024 10.5281/zenodo.11486081.

Altafani, D., Bleil de Souza, C., Pezzica, C., Marques, G., Dalcin, A. (2024) Communication - Immediate Actions: Road-Network Accesses Preservation Porto Alegre and its Metropolita-n Region Vulnerability Analysis – May 2024 Floodings 10.5281/zenodo.11489615.

Altafani, D., How Porto Alegre's Metropolitan Road Network Coped with the Floodings? (2024) 10.5281/zenodo.11490519.

Berghauer Pont, M., Stavroulaki, I., Gil, J., & Marcus, L., Serra, M., Hausleitner, B., Ols-son, J., Dhanani, A. (2017). Quantitative Comparison of Cities: Distribution of street and building types based on density and centrality measures. In: proceedings of the 11th International Space Syntax Symposium 2017 - University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal.

Decreto Nº 57.596, de 1º de Maio de 2024". (2024) Diário Oficial do Rio Grande do Sul (in Brazilian Portuguese). Rio Grande do Sul, 1 May 2024. Archived from the original 02-05-2024. Retrieved: 06-05-2024

depthmapX development team. (2020). depthmapX (Version 0.8.0) [Computer software]. Retrieved from <https://github.com/SpaceGroupUCL/depthmapX/>

Governo do Estado do Rio Grande do Sul (2024). Impactos das Chuvas e Cheias Extremas no Rio Grande do Sul em Maio de 2024. EMATER/RS, Secretaria de Desenvolvimento Rural (SDR), Porto Alegre, 1st June, 2024.

Hillier, B., and J. Hanson. 1984. The Social Logic of Space. Reprint: Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

Hillier, B., Yang, T., & Turner, A. (2012). Normalising least angle choice in Depthmap and it opens up new perspectives on the global and local analysis of city space. *Journal of Space Syntax*, 3(2), 155–193.

OpenStreetMap contributors. (2025) Planet dump [Data file from 01/05/2024]. Retrieved from <https://planet.openstreetmap.org>

Possanti, I.; Müller, J.; Ruhoff, A. (Eds.). (2024). Cheias no Rio Grande do Sul - Base de dados e informações geográficas na Região Hidrográfica do Lago Guaíba e na Lagoa dos Patos em 2024. UFRGS. Available at: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/a81d69f4bccf42989609e3fe64d8ef48>

QGIS, Pritzen, version 3.34 (2024) Available at: <http://www.qgis.org/en/site/index.html>

Rio Grande do Sul Flood Emergency: Snapshot #4" (2024). United Nations. 7 July 2024. Retrieved 14-07-2024.

Turner, A. (2001). Angular Analysis. In S. Peponis, J., Wineman, J. & Bafna (Ed.), *Proceedings 3rd International Space Syntax Symposium* (pp. 30.1-30.11).

Van Nes, A; Yamu, C. (2021) Introduction to space syntax in urban studies. Springer Nature. ISBN: 9783030591403, 9783030591403, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-59140-3>

For further information about this research, please reach altafani.d@cardiff.ac.uk

Welsh School of Architecture
Ysgol Pensaernïaeth Cymru

MEMBROS DA
PESQUISAS HIDRÁULICAS

GESPLA
GRUPO DE PESQUISA EM
Planejamento Urbano
e Paisagem